

PYRONES AND RELATED COMPOUNDS. PART VII. ACTION OF
ETHYL *o*-FORMATE ON DIACETYLACETONE

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Ethyl-*o*-formate reacts with the two methylene groups of diacetylacetone to form a diethoxymethylene compound which immediately undergoes ring-closure and transforms to form 2-ethyl-3-acetoxy-5-acetyl- $\Delta^3:3:4:6$ -cyclopentenone which undergoes hydrolysis with a concentrated solution of potassium hydroxide and on acidifying gives 2-ethyl-3-hydroxy- $\Delta^3:3:4:6$ -cyclopentenone. It forms an acetyl derivative.

Diacetylacetone has the structure (I) and contains in its molecule two reactive methylene groups. It could not be condensed with sodium and formic ester for the simple reason that it forms its own sodium derivative which inhibits further action. Further, it undergoes self-condensation in presence of basic condensing agents like piperidine (Kaushal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 17) to form dihydroxydimethylacetylnaphthalene.

Diacetylacetone on heating with *ortho*formic ester in presence of acetic anhydride gives a crystalline solid (m.p. 106°). The analysis of the compound corresponds to the formula $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$, and on treatment with strong potash solution on warming it yields a solid potassium derivative which, in turn on acidifying, affords a product (m.p. 177°) of the formula $\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$ which with acetic anhydride or acetyl chloride gives a monoacetate of the composition $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ (m.p. 135°). These reactions could only be explained in the following manner.

At first by the reaction of *ortho*formic ester on the reactive methylene groups of diacetylacetone (I), the diethoxymethylene diacetylacetone (II) is formed which could not be isolated as it readily undergoes ring-closure to form the compound (III). The latter undergoes transformation to give (IV, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}$) in which both the ethyl and acetyl groups migrating and exchanging places. This is somewhat peculiar transformation which has been noticed in this case. There are reasons to believe that the ethyl group migrates as Levy and Langrave (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 1032) working on the rearrangement of asymmetric glycols have shown that the ethyl group is capable of migration. Thus 1:1-diphenylbutane oxide (V) gives on isomerisation 1:1-diphenylbutanone (VI) and 1:1-diphenylethylacetaldehyde (VII).

The compound (IV, $R_1 = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}$; $R = (\text{H}_3\text{CO}_2)$) on treatment with concentrated solution of KOH is hydrolysed somewhat like acetylacetone itself and the two acetyl groups are removed resulting in the formation of the potassium derivative (IV, $R_1 = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}$; $R = \text{OK}$) which when decomposed with acids gives the cyclopentenone derivative (IV, $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R = \text{OH}$), the hydroxyl of which readily reacts with acetic anhydride to form the monoacetyl derivative (IV, $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2$).

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Diacetylacetone with orthoFormic Ester: Formation of (IV, $R = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2$; $R_1 = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}$).—Diacetylacetone (5.5 g.), orthoformic ester (12 g.) and acetic anhydride (25 drops) were refluxed with an air condenser on a sand-bath for 4 hours when a portion of the reaction mixture solidified on a watchglass. On cooling some solid separated which was filtered and the filtrate mixed with an equal volume of water and allowed to crystallise. By the next day star-shaped crystalline needles separated which were filtered and the filtrate gave a second crop. This was somewhat gummy and therefore purified by rubbing with alcohol; total yield 2 g. It was crystallised from benzene and petrol as long, thin needles, m.p. 106° . (Found: C, 63.5, 63.8; H, 5.3, 6.0. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 63.5; H, 5.8 per cent).

If however, acetic anhydride is used in molecular proportion, only a gum results from which no definite product could be isolated.

Action of concentrated solution of KOH on (IV, $R_1 = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}$; $R = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2$); Formation of (IV, $R = \text{OH}$; $R_1 = \text{H}$).—The compound (IV, $R = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2$; $R_1 = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}$) (2g.) was treated with 50% KOH solution when a yellow potassium derivative was formed on warming. It was filtered and washed with a little water in which the potassium derivative was sparingly soluble. The potassium derivative was suspended in water and decomposed with hydrochloric acid when it gave the compound (IV, $R = \text{OH}$; $R_1 = \text{H}$) as a canary yellow solid which was filtered, washed and dried, m.p. 177° . The aqueous filtrate from the potassium derivative on acidifying with hydrochloric acid also gave a little more of the same solid but this was impure and gummy; total yield 15 g. On crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 177° . (Found: C, 67.8; H, 5.8. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$ requires C, 67.7; H, 6.4 per cent).

This appears to form phenylhydrazone in glacial acetic acid solution.

The acetyl derivative (IV, $R = \text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2$; $R_1 = \text{H}$) was obtained in the usual manner by boiling the compound (m.p. 177°) with acetic anhydride or acetyl chloride and a drop of sulphuric acid. On cooling and pouring the reaction product in water it came out as almost colourless plates having shining lustre, m.p. 135° . (Found: C, 65.5; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 65.1; H, 6.1 per cent).

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